

ACOUSTIC MICROSCOPY FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPOSITES

B. R. Tittmann
Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics
Penn State University
University Park, PA 16802

ABSTRACT

Ultrasonic data for the characterization of Carbon-Carbon Composite are presented. The sensors used to obtain the data consist of a plate wave generator/receiver and an acoustic emission detector for in-process characterization and of a scanning acoustic microscope for post-process characterization. With the aid of high temperature waveguides the process sensors are shown to detect the in-situ changes in some of the key properties of plates of Carbon-Carbon during pyrolysis in the range of temperatures from 25C to 900C. In particular, changes in stiffness as a result of microcracking and decomposition are readily detected and are useful to guide/revise the time-temperature profile of the carbonization heat treatment. The acoustic data show a variety of interesting features giving insight into the microstructural changes as a result of the heat treatment. Among these are: the subsurface microstructure before and after pyrolysis as obtained with the acoustic microscope, the difference in the behavior of the symmetric and antisymmetric plate modes during pyrolysis, and the observation of a minimum in the temperature dependent modulus at about 650C.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Nondestructive Evaluation; In-Process Characterization; Carbon-Carbon; Scanning Acoustic Microscopy; Acoustic Emission.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report is based on the results of recent work carried out to demonstrate the viability of acoustic sensors to characterize changes in microstructure during First Carbonization of Carbon/Carbon. In particular, we have demonstrated on flat plates up to one foot square in size that the acoustic behavior before and after pyrolysis are significantly different. About 30 experimental runs have been carried out, which show that acoustic emission and plate mode propagation provide valuable information in advance of any delaminations so that the potential exists for making corrective changes during the processing treatment.

The manufacturing process of carbon-carbon is a long, high-risk procedure with is based on empirical methods. Variations in the constituent materials, the part geometry, or time/temperature profiles during first carbonization may produce damage that is difficult to diagnose and expensive to correct. Recent work[1-9] has shown that during first carbonization, matrix cracking is a consequence of "normal" carbonization. In fact microcracks are desirable, in that they release stress and create an open network, that allows the release of gases formed by the chemical changes. On the other hand, delaminations are intolerable because they reduce through-thickness stiffness and buckling strength. They are typically caused by excessively fast heating of relatively large and/or thick sheet material and represent "anomalous" carbonization. The goal of the manufacturer is to achieve carbonization in as short a time as possible but without excessive damage from delaminations. The key is the monitoring of internal microstructure during the course of carbonization in order to optimize the process. Recent work on ultrasonic sensors shows that these are especially suitable for monitoring microstructure because the acoustic interaction with the material is noninvasive and because the sensor data provide direct information on the evolution of microstructure. Acoustic Emission sensors have now been shown feasible and viable sensor techniques. The objective of this program has been to develop the acoustic sensor technologies and the development of models to relate the acoustic data to the microstructure in as quantitative a way as possible and enhance our understanding of the cause and nature of the changes during carbonization.

2. TECHNICAL DISCUSSION

2.1 Sample Description The material used in these experiments was 2-D, thin resin (K-641) matrix composite provided by Kaiser Airotech Inc. in a state just prior to first carbonization; i.e. after the curing process. In this state the samples were typically hard, brittle and dense. The resin has had some cross linking. The open pore porosity was less than 1% and the density about 1.42 gm/cm³. The weave was 7 over, one under with the fibers nominally 10 microns in diameter and the lamina about 150-200 microns thick.

As the samples were heated to 700°C they pyrolyzed with the liberation of organic volatiles CH₄, H₄, H₂O, CO₂ and CO.

After the heat treatment, the samples had shrunk in thickness by about 7%, lost about 14% of their weight and had a much higher volume fraction of cracks and voids. The open pore porosity was about 20% and the density about 1.32 gm/cm³.

2.2 Experimental Approach Figure 1 shows the experimental apparatus used in the process monitoring measurements. It consists of a furnace and an array of sensors, including a mass flow meter, active and passive acoustic sensors, thermocouple gauges, gas chromatographs and a weight loss sensor. A desktop computer collects the data and provides temperature

control. Another computer operates in order to carry out material state monitoring, prognosis, planning and explanation. Only the acoustic sensors are addressed here, whereas the design and operation of the other sensors are described in Reference 3 and the planning, explanation and control station are described in Reference 9.

Since the carbonization process involves the heating of the component to 900°C, the acoustic sensors are attached to the component via waveguides (1/8 inch thick) fashioned from high temperature alloys (stainless steel or Inconel 718). The waveguides are cylindrical rods which are threaded at opposite ends of the sample. This connection is bonded adhesively using a drop of K-641 resin which is allowed to polymerize at approximately 160°C prior to each run. The transducers are narrow band and are clamped to a small platform which is brazed to the top of each waveguide outside the furnace. Transducers and waveguides are coupled acoustically using a high viscosity silicone oil.

The post process ultrasonic equipment was a UH-3 Olympus Scanning Acoustic Microscope SAM with a operational frequency range of 25MHz to 1 GHz. The SAM was used to provide conventional C-scan images at the low frequencies and high resolution images at 400 MHz. These high resolution images were obtained with a high numerical aperture (120 degree) lens, which produces acoustic surface waves in addition to focussing bulk waves. The resulting images are rich in contrast and show microcracks particularly well - a major goal in the present context.

2.3 Microstructural information obtained from ultrasonic data. Several of the samples were characterized by measuring the elastic stiffness constants and one representative data set is shown in Table I. The longitudinal velocity and the corresponding modulus c_{11} are seen to diminish drastically with carbonization treatment.

The scanning acoustic microscope SAM was used to image the samples. After the heat treatment the samples exhibited many intralaminar microcracks and some interlaminar cracks. Because of the reflectivities of the fibers when seen edge-on and sideways the optical micrographs left considerable uncertainty on the extent of the interlaminar cracks. As Fig2 and Fig. 3 show the acoustic images had no such difficulties. There are several interesting features about these images. Among these are the apparent periodicity of the intralaminar cracks and the occasional presence of interlaminar cracks associated with some of the intralaminar cracks. These features are in qualitative agreement with modeling calculations (10) and indicate how an intralaminar crack can lead to a delamination under special conditions, such as high local stress produced by trapped volatiles.

The presence of so many microcracks suggests considerable Acoustic Emission (AE) activity. Our method for parameterizing AE activity on a statistical basis involves counting threshold crossings at each of several amplitudes which are evenly spaced on a log scale. The threshold amplitudes selected were 31.6 microvolts, 178 microvolts, 1 millivolt and 5.62

millivolts, all referenced to the transducer output. The most sensitive setting was approximately 7dB above background electronic noise. Figure 4 shows the AE activity of the lowest threshold as a function of temperature during a "normal" run without delaminations. The sample was a thin plate of approximately 12 by 12 by 1/8 inch dimensions. The heat up rate was 10°C/hour. Not shown are the cool down data. There are two periods of intense activity, the first while heating between 400°C and 600°C and the second while cooling. The effects of cool down are treated in Reference 4. Also shown are plate mode arrival times for both the compressional and the flexural plate modes showing that the compressional waves are influenced by the presence of cracks concomitant with a decrease in stiffness.

The data suggest three stages of AE activity correlated with corresponding stages of microcracking. The results are consistent with the interpretation in terms of a competition between two main physical changes which are concomitant with the chemical changes. The two sources of stress are the shrinkage of the matrix and the thermal expansion of the matrix and fiber material.

The cracks within the "as cured" material can be explained by the difference in thermal expansion between the fibers, which actually have a negative coefficient of thermal expansion along their length, and the matrix material. Although the plate is able to shrink homogeneously during cooling in the direction perpendicular to the laminations, the fibers prevent this from occurring in the plane of the laminations. Therefore, at temperatures below the cure temperature the fiber bundles support a compressive load along their length, and the resulting tensile load in the matrix in the plane orthogonal to the plane of the lamination and parallel to the fiber direction causes the cracks observed.

As the sample is heated these cracks start to close, and should be closed completely as the sample once again reaches the curing temperature, at approximately 160°C. At higher temperatures the fiber bundles go into tension along their length and the matrix goes into compression in the plane orthogonal to the plane of the lamination and parallel to the fiber direction. Since the fibers can support these tensile loads, as long as the matrix remains in compression, the observed lack of cracking and associated AE is a consequence.

In stage 2 (400°C - 650°C) the phenolic resin starts to break down chemically. Gases evolve and are released from the specimen through the pre-existing crack structure. Even though the resin is shrinking volumetrically at this point it is still not in tension because of the residual thermally induced compressive stresses. In fact, the carbonization and associated matrix shrinkage must progress to a degree before the stresses in the matrix once again become tensile in the direction orthogonal to the fiber axes. At this point, inferred by AE to be between 400° and 500°C, severe microcracking starts to occur. This continues with increasing temperature until carbonization has been completed. Finally in stage 3, the effects of thermal expansion again dominate causing the matrix to be in compression. In this regime gas

analysis measurements show a substantial evolution in H₂ gas. It is conjectured that there may be a phase transformation giving rise to some additional shrinkage and the AE activity shows some microcracking.

The scenario described above is thought to hold for "normal" runs in which the heating rate is low and no significant damage such as delaminations are produced. AE is caused by a sudden release of localized stress. Sources of stress during carbonization are the transformation shrinkage of the matrix, differential thermal expansion and then entrapment of evolved gasses. The release of stress is typically associated with crack initiation and crack growth/extension.

In carbon-carbon pyrolysis microcracking is normal and desirable, because the goal is to form an open, interconnected network of cracks to enable the escape of evolved gases. Desirable microcracks include fiber-matrix cracks and matrix-matrix cracks. Fiber-matrix cracks arise as a result of the unbonding between the reinforcing fibers and the matrix. Fiber-matrix cracks developing between neighboring sites link up and produce matrix-matrix cracks which eventually extend through the matrix of a given ply typically in a direction perpendicular to the fibers. The AE waveforms associated with fiber-matrix and matrix-matrix cracks typically involve short duration times and relatively low amplitudes. In contrast, delaminations typically cover larger areas and therefore the characteristic duration times are comparatively long and the waveform amplitudes are high.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The use of ultrasonic sensors has been shown to be successful for the characterization during the first carbonization of carbon-carbon panels. Our understanding of the microstructure of the material has advanced as a result of a combination of ultrasonic techniques including AE, plate mode propagation and scanning acoustic microscopy. These results open the door to the acquisition of a statistically meaningful database for application to process control in the factory whether for process simulation or production.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Support from Penn State University and the Office of Naval Research under Contract N00014-87-C-0724 are gratefully acknowledged.

5. REFERENCES

1. "Process Science for 2D Carbon-Carbon Exit Losses", prepared by Aerojet Strategic Propulsion Co., AFWAL Report No. TR 86-4028, July 1986.

2. K. T. Clemens and S. C. Brown, "Real-Time Acoustic Emission Monitoring/Control Technique for Carbonization of 2-D Phenolic-Carbon Composites", 8th JANNAF RNTS Mfg., Patrick AFB, October 1986.
3. W. J. Pardee, M. R. Mitchell, A. Gupta, F. Montgomery and J. Sheehan, "Effect of Carbonization Kinetics on In-Process Mechanical Properties", in "Intelligent Processing of Materials" (edited by H. Wadley and W. Eckhart) Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society publication, pp. 195-207 (1990).
4. J. R. Bulau, "AE Monitoring for Control of Carbon-Carbon Pyrolysis", Proceedings of IEEE 1988 Ultrasonics Symposium (B. R. McAvoy, Editor), IEEE Cat. No. 88 CH 2578-3, pp. 1057-1063 (1988).
5. B. R. Tittmann and J. R. Bulau, "Acoustic Emission and Ultrasonics Sensing for Carbon-Carbon Pyrolysis Monitoring", in "Intelligent Processing of Materials" (edited by H. Wadley and W. Eckhart) Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society publication, pp. 267-274 (1990).
6. B. R. Tittmann, "Acoustical Studies of Damage Mechanism in Carbon-Carbon during First Carbonization", Proceedings of the 1989 IEEE Ultrasonics Symposium, IEEE Catalog No. 0090-5607/89/0000-0627, pp 627-630.
7. B. R. Tittmann, "High Temperature Young's Modulus of Carbon-Carbon Composite Material" Proceedings of The ASME Symposium on Nondestructive Evaluation of Materials and Structures using Vibration and Acoustic Techniques (P. K. Raju, Editor) NDE-Vol 6, pp 69-72, 1989.
8. B. R. Tittmann and J. R. Bulau, "NDE of Delaminations during Processing of Carbon-Carbon Composites", Proceedings of the International Symposium on Acoustical Imaging, Santa Barbara, Ca, 1989, in press.
9. W. J. Pardee, R. C. Addison, D. J. Miley, B. S. Seely, M. A. Shaff and B. R. Tittmann of Rockwell International; A. Gupta of Ioptix; and F. Montgomery and J. Sheehan of General Atomics, "Intelligent Control of Carbon-Carbon Pyrolysis", in "Intelligent Processing of Materials" (edited by H. Wadley and W. Eckhart) Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society publication, pp. 73-81 (1990).
10. R. Clayton, private communication.

6. FIGURES

TABLE 1. ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF C/C

Sample Condition	Density gm/cc	Velocity in Thickns Long. (m/s)	Dir Shear (m/s)	C11 GPa	C22 GPa	C66 GPa	C12 GPa	Anisotropy Factor
Before Pyrolysis	1.42	3298	1940 cntct 1926	15	20	5.3	5.4	0.73
After Pyrolysis	1.32	1523	1520 cntct 1505	3.4	13	3	1.1	0.5

Figure 1 Carbon-Carbon Data Acquisition System

Figure 2 400 MHz Scanning Acoustic Micrograph Scan Width 2mm

Figure 3 400 MHz Scanning Acoustic Micrograph Scan Width 1mm

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 Acoustic Emission (a) and Lamb Wave Delay (b) during "normal" runs without delamination. (Ref. 5)

7. BIOGRAPHY

B. R. Tittmann: Penn State University, Bayard Kunkle Professor of Engineering, Dept. of Engineering Science and Mechanics, B.S., Physics, George Washington University, Ph.D., Physics, UCLA in 1965. Dr. Tittmann has a broad background in Physical Acoustics gained during his tenure of nearly 25 years at the Science Center of Rockwell International. He is probably best known for his work in geophysical ultrasonics, NDE and acoustic sensors. He investigated and explained the dramatic reduction of anelastic attenuation of lunar return samples when subjected to lunar environment. His main interest is in material characterization, using surface acoustic wave dispersion, internal friction, ultrasonic attenuation, and diffraction to characterize polymers, ceramics and metal alloys. He is currently engaged in studies of coatings and thin films with the aid of acoustic microscopy and the use of acoustic sensors for in-situ monitoring of materials processes. He has about 170 publications and is a Fellow of the Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers, a member of the Acoustical Society of America and the American Physical Society.

